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Annotation: This article discusses ways to learn a foreign language more conveniently through various games. Through these games, it becomes easier for schoolchildren to learn a foreign language.

Key words: schools, foreign languages, learnin, traditional methods, ability.

Since learning foreign languages is gaining importance today, languages are taught not only in higher education institutions, schools, but also in pre-school educational institutions. If the lessons are not taught with unique methods and interesting methods, it can become a difficult task to attract students to the lesson. If lessons are changed from traditional methods and made interesting, this not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but also prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson. There are a number of interesting games in the process of teaching English and Russian. It is worth mentioning that in teaching language to children, it is necessary to use such games in which all students can participate equally and learn new things from the lesson, for example, new vocabulary can be memorized, if this process is repeated every day, the student's vocabulary increases to a higher level. It is inappropriate to start the lesson with grammar concepts, especially for younger students, because it causes them to quickly get bored. As a result, interest in the class may fade. With them, even the process of greeting should be started in a non-traditional way, for example, the method of starting the lesson with some kind

of greeting English song when the teacher enters is an effective method. If the lesson continues in this way, the students will not lose their attention to one task during the lesson. They even look forward to English lessons. Of course, all this should be organized by the teacher, and it is the pedagogue's responsibility. Therefore, some types of games can be mentioned to make learning a foreign language interesting.

"Role-playing games" can be used to improve the effectiveness of English and Russian language lessons. The advantage of this game is that it is played based on the situation. This game is not only useful for learning science, but also helps to develop mental ability. In this game, topics are selected and children create dialogues. For example, the passenger's conversation while stopping the taxi, or the conversations in clothing stores - all of this is spoken and shown in English. It is in this game that we can use the tactics of working with a group, that is, dividing students into groups and dividing them into different topics. In this case, competition also occurs. Competition is a criterion for growth. If a group that does well in a task is encouraged, the rest of the students will also be motivated. In addition, it is appropriate to use didactic games to conduct English lessons meaningfully.

OBJECT- this game serves to increase students' vocabulary. We know that the most important direction in learning a foreign language is memorizing a new word. Considering the characteristics of students, each student memorizes vocabulary in his own way. We are sure that learning new words through games is suitable for everyone and makes the process easier. In our game mentioned above, during the lesson, 15 items from the classroom are placed on the table and the students come and look at these items. The items are covered and then the students have to write what they see on the board in English for a certain amount of time. The student who spells the most words correctly is the winner. In order to ensure the quality of this game, I can say that in order to attract students who are in this situation and did not participate in the lesson, it would be appropriate if they were given the task of making one sentence for the names of these items, and this it also prevents indifference.

Pictionary is a game familiar to most English language teachers and learners, a word game with its name and a picture in it. You can use a normal whiteboard or a magnetic board to draw in this game. Students of the class are divided into two groups, and a table is drawn on both sides of the board for each team. The scores of the teams are recorded in these tables. Word names are written on the desk and turned upside

down. Students from each group take turns choosing one of the hidden words and drawing it on the board. The team that gets it first will be awarded a point. This game also sharpens the minds of the students. We can also say that the use of images is a tactic that attracts readers quickly, especially if it is created by the students themselves.

Taboo words game (Forbidden words) is a fun game that helps students use synonyms and their meanings. The use of synonyms ensures the fluency of speech and the beauty of speech. Especially in the English language, it is important to avoid mistakes in the use of words, because many words in the English language with the same meaning are used according to the context of the sentence. This game will help you to be careful in this regard. In this, groups are formed, that is, students sit opposite each other. Each team chooses one person from their team to sit in the chair opposite them. The teacher goes behind the students and holds a word written on a large piece of paper. Students sitting in their seats should not be able to see this word. There will be some time for the member of the team sitting in the seat to say the word that the teacher is holding.

Tennis game - the purpose of this game is to increase the speed of the students. This game is similar to a chain game and takes place within the chosen theme. In this case, a new word should be added to the last letter of the spoken word, for example, if the topic name is "Animals", if it starts with the word "Tiger" without deviating from the topic, the second participant continues with "rabbit". In this way, the game continues. A student who stops during the game and does not answer for 5 minutes is removed from the game and continues with the rest of the students. Play the game with the class, i.e. it will be very interesting and fun to play with many people. This game can also be played by changing the theme. At the same time, in the process of organizing the games, connecting them with different technical tools. also serves to increase interest. Because in today's rapidly developing age, not all young people, teenagers and adults are indifferent to modern technologies. Therefore, an effective result can be achieved by organizing interesting science games on computers. Indeed, in teaching also teaches grammatical concepts ladi, because it is indicated in the lesson plans of the teachers. But there is also a game to make this process easier and fun. For example, subject word groups. They should be able to learn and distinguish word groups well. Students can be given the task of writing only words related to the noun phrase while listening to music in English, and then the student can be given another word phrase. In this way, the topic is strengthened, this method can be used in the

process of passing other topics. It can also be organized as a cultural activity for students. When using games, we can change them depending on the knowledge and age of the children, that is, make them easier or more complicated. The purpose of these above-mentioned games is to strengthen the memory of the students, to increase their mental capacity, quickness, intelligence, to remember new words easily, and most importantly, to organize the lesson meaningfully. Today, the educational process is mainly carried out in a traditional way, but at all stages of the educational system, continuous learning of foreign languages, as well as improving the qualifications of teachers and teaching with modern educational and methodological materials provision requires further improvement.

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